

Challenges Encountered by Intermediate English Teachers in the Implementation of PHIL-IRI in Relation to Learners Reading Performance

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14489580

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Abstract:

This study sought to assess the challenges encountered by Intermediate English Teachers in the implementation of PHIL-IRI in relation to learners reading performance. There were 38 teacher respondents included in this study under the District of Manjuyod 1. The total number of respondents were 38 teachers who will assess the level of challenges encountered by Intermediate English Teachers in the implementation of PHIL-IRI in relation to learners reading performance. The baseline data was collected from 38 public elementary school teachers handling intermediate level. The variables included were age, number of years as English teacher, highest educational attainment. The study sought to establish the degree of challenges encountered by Intermediate English in the implementation of PHIL-IRI in relation to learners reading performance on these phases: before implementation, during implementation, after implementation. A self-made questionnaire was validated and employed to measure the responses of the respondents. The findings of the study indicated these phases of concern. The degree of challenges encountered by Intermediate English Teachers in the implementation of PHIL-IRI in relation to learner's reading performance showed that before implementation respondents were able to land the "Moderate Degree" and during the implementation and after implementation both the respondents were able to land the "Low Degree".

Keywords: Challenges encountered, Intermediate English Teachers, implementation of PHIL-IRI, reading performance

Introduction:

Nature of the Problem

In teaching fields many challenges were encountered by teachers. Working as an English teacher, affords challenges every day. The teacher has to deal with many students at a time with different levels of ability, motivation, special interests, and experiences. Teaching children to read accurately, fluently, and with adequate comprehension in the English language is one of the main goals of intermediate education. Reading is critical because a great deal of formal education depends upon being able to read with understanding.

Reading is a very important skill for learners to attain to be functionally literate in today's organization. It develops the capabilities of an individual that will help him contribute meaningfully to society (Davis, 2016). The Department Order No. 14, segment 2018 states that the Department of Education (DepEd) bolsters Every Child a Reader Program, which intends to make each Filipino youngster a reader and an author at his/her level. Subsequently, the DepEd through the Bureau of Learning Delivery-Teaching and Learning Division (BLD-TLD) will keep on managing the Revised Informal Reading Inventory (PHIL-IRI) appraisal to students openly grade schools across the nation viable School year 2018-2019. The Phil-IRI used as a classroom-based assessment tool aims to measure and describe the learners' reading performance in both English and Filipino languages in oral reading, silent reading and listening comprehension. These three types of assessment aim to determine the learner's independent, instructional and frustration levels.

The Phil-IRI data shall also serve as one of the bases in planning, designing/redesigning the reading instruction of the teachers and the school's reading programs or activities to improve the overall school's reading performance.

Reading helps students think critically and improves reading comprehension skills, which is beneficial in every subject area measured in this study. However, the benefits of pleasure reading do not end in the classroom. Students take the skills they have honed through reading into adulthood and, in turn, into the workforce and society.

In the past years, reading is a problem since most of the learners in the intermediate level has difficulty in the comprehension level. During this pandemic, the researcher motivates to conduct this study since modular distance learning is being implemented and face to face is not allowed, learners cannot be given assessment for reading and remediation. The teachers gave the reading materials to the parents during module distribution and instruct them to guide their child. When the reading assessment came, the teacher called the parents thru cellular phone and let the child read orally while the teacher is listening thru phone call.

Through this study the DepEd will be able to address to the DEPED officials of some possible remediation to address the problem both the challenges of the teachers in implementing the PHIL-IRI and as well as the reading problem of the pupils.

Current State of Knowledge

Manaog (2019), states the news hit us hard, teachers, especially since we conscientiously and religiously labor six days a week in teaching our lessons to our students, teaching them with the prescribed materials and even working longer hours to comply with and submit the needed paperwork. He states that he identifies where this comes from. He attributes that the increasing number of slow readers and non-readers to a string of factors, namely: the lack of study habits among our pupils; the lack of contact hours in teaching; the effects of technology, internet and the social media; and the effects of even the Department of Education's Child Protection Policy (DepEd Order 40, series of 2012). Tavera and Casinillo (2020), shows in their study that there were significant relationships between knowledge acquisition practices of learners and their prior knowledge, vocabulary and knowledge acquisition practices of teachers versus vocabulary level of the learners. There were also significant relationships between prior knowledge and vocabulary to the reading comprehension of the learners.

In the study of Candilas (2019), the results confirmed that there is a positive significant relationship between electronic media exposures in science fiction and adventure to student-participants' reading comprehension skills in terms of sequencing events, predicting outcomes, and identifying themes. However, a host of other factors may affect students' reading comprehension skill in noting detail. Based from the findings drawn, the study calls for the need to reinforce the use of electronic media in increasing students' reading comprehension skills. Moreover, the result of this investigation can be used as a baseline data in making instructional materials, which presuppose the integration of electronic media activities.

Further, Leaño (2019), mentioned about Speaking difficulties of Philippine indigenous learners in English Semantics findings revealed that all the five indigenous learner-participants demonstrated English vocabulary deficiency to name depicted objects in the surroundings. They had struggles in reciting week-days, months and in citing common Philippine events. They had difficulty in conveying illustrated antonyms and synonyms. These findings denote a language intervention to improve essential skills in English semantics. This study can be an alternative to investigate problems in other language literacy domains. When a learner could not pronounce well the English language it would be difficult for them to read and comprehend English reading text which may lead to poor comprehension skills in reading. It becomes a challenge for teacher to teach learners specially those who are used to speaking their dialect.

Also, Jala (2020) concluded on her study about Pupils' Reading Comprehension, Problem-Solving Skills and Academic Performance that reading comprehension is a contributory factor to the improvement of pupils' academic performance and problem-solving performance. The researcher recommends that school administrators look into the possibilities of providing more supplementary materials in the form of books and other reading materials so that pupils can use it for further learning and to organize seminars and workshops, special trainings in order to fully equip the teachers with more knowledge and skills in teaching reading strategies. Teachers may organize functional educational programs, remedial classes and enrichment activities to improve pupils' comprehension skills through systematic comprehension instruction.

Theoretical Underpinnings

This study anchored on Schema theory by Anderson (1994: 469) presents research showing that recall of information in a text is affected by the reader's schemata and explains that "a reader comprehends a message when he is able to bring to mind a schema that gives an account of the objects and events described in the message". Comprehension is the process of "activating or constructing a schema that provides a coherent explanation of objects and events mentioned in a discourse" (Anderson, 1994: 473). For Anderson and Pearson (1988: 38), comprehension is the interaction between old and new information. They emphasize: "To say that one has comprehended a text is to say that she has found a mental 'home' for the information in the text, or else that she has modified an existing mental

home in order to accommodate that new information". Therefore, a learner's schemata will restructure itself to accommodate new information as that information is added to the system (Omaggio, 1993).

Objectives

This study aimed to determine the challenges encountered by Intermediate English Teachers in the implementation of PHIL-IRI in relation to learner's reading performance in one of the districts of a large-sized division in central Philippines during the School Year 2020-2021. Specifically, it seeks answers to the following questions: 1) the degree of challenges encountered by Intermediate English Teachers in the implementation of PHIL IRI in relation to learner's reading performance based to the phases of before implementation, during implementation, and , after implementation; 2) the degree of challenges encountered by Intermediate English Teachers in the implementation of PHIL-IRI in relation to learners reading performance when grouped according to the aforementioned phases; 3) the level of learners reading performance based on grade levels of grade 4, grade 5, and grade 6; 4) the significant difference in the degree of challenges encountered by Intermediate English Teachers when they are grouped and compared based to the aforementioned variables; and 5) the significant relationship between the degree of challenges encountered by Intermediate English Teachers and the level of comprehension skills on intermediate learner's reading performance.

Methodology:

This section presents the discussion of the research methodology used, the subjects and respondents of the study, the research instruments used, the validity and reliability of the instruments, the procedure for data gathering, and the statistical tools and procedure for data analysis.

Research Design

This study employed the descriptive research design to determine the challenges encountered by Intermediate English Teachers in the implementation of PHIL-IRI in relation to learner's reading performance in one of the districts of a large-sized division in central Philippines. Descriptive research method provides a way to describe the nature of the situation as it exists at the time of the study. Descriptive research design is appropriate for studies which aim to find out what prevail in the present condition on relationship held opinions and beliefs, processes and effects and developing trends. It includes evaluation of the studies that were analyzed. According to Manuel and Medel (2016), descriptive research involves the description, recording, analysis and interpretation of the present native composition of process of phenomena. Descriptive research designs are also valuable to have an important knowledge about the present situation of the study. It can be yielded to enrich data that least to import a recommendation. Factors influencing challenges encountered by English subject teachers will be studied to find out prevailing condition that may address current needs and problems.

Study Respondents

The respondents of this study are the Grade four, five and six English Teachers in 14 public elementary in one of the districts of a large-sized division in central Philippines. Since the number of respondents were manageable, Random Sampling was not employed as all the respondents were considered respondents of the study.

Instruments

The study used a self-made instrument to gather baseline-data. The instruments were divided into two parts: Part 1 contains queries on respondents' profile such as age, sex, length of service, and highest educational attainment. Part 2 is the questionnaire that consists of 30 items on the challenges encountered by Intermediate English Teachers' in the implementation of PHIL-IRI in relation to learner's reading performance. To make sure that the study runs smoothly, the following procedure was employed. There was a letter of request addressed to the Schools Division Superintendent for the conduct of the study within District I to be submitted for approval. Upon approval, letter requests were distributed to the school heads of concerned schools. After securing the approval for the second request, questionnaires were administered to target respondents. The respondents are asked to rate each item using the five-point Likert's scale which contains the following scores: 5 – Very High; 4 – High; 3 – Moderate; 2 – Low and 1 – always often. The research instrument was subjected to validity (4.84-excellent) and reliability (0.896-good). All of them were interpreted as worthy and good; respectively.

Data Gathering Procedure

After the instrument was found valid and reliable, the researcher observed the following processes in gathering the data needed for this study. First, the researcher sent a letter addressed to the Schools Division Superintendent of the Division Office for his approval to conduct this study. Second, the researcher sought the approval of the District Supervisor for the administration of the questionnaires. Upon approval, letter requests were distributed to the school

heads of concerned schools within District I. After securing the approval for the second request, questionnaires were administered to target respondents. The data gathered from the responses of the respondents were tallied and tabulated using the appropriate statistical tools. The raw data were transformed into numerical code guided by a coding manual. This allowed computer processing, statistical derivations and tabular presentation. The Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) was used in the computer processing of the encoded data.

Data Analysis and Statistical Treatment

Objective No.1 used a descriptive-analytical scheme and mean determine the degree of challenges encountered by Intermediate English Teachers in the implementation of PHIL-IRI in relation to learner’s reading performance when grouped according to the following phases: before implementation, during implementation, after implementation.

Objective No.2 used a descriptive-analytical scheme and mean to determine the degree of challenges encountered by Intermediate English Teachers in the implementation of PHIL-IRI in relation to learners reading performance.

Objective No.3 used a descriptive-analytical scheme and mean to determine the level of learners reading performance in English in grades 4,5 and 6.

Objective No. 4 used a descriptive-analytical scheme and mean to determine the significant difference in the degree of challenges encountered by Intermediate English Teachers when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables.

Objective No. 5 used a descriptive-analytical scheme and mean to determine the degree of challenges encountered by Intermediate English Teachers and the level of comprehension skills on intermediate level learners in English subject.

Ethical Consideration

The protection of human subjects through the application of appropriate ethical principles is important in all research study. The principle of voluntary participation requires that people not be coerced into participating in research (Trochim, 2021). As to the informed consent, the participants were fully informed about the procedures and risks involved in research and gave their consent to participate. As such, participants were entirely enlightened about the procedures of the entire research and were encouraged to participate by signing a consent. Additionally, several safeguards were in place to minimize harm in a research protocol that involves vulnerable participants or sensitive topics. (Peter, 2015). As to the confidentiality of the results, the participants were assured that identifying information will not be made available to anyone who is not directly involved in the study. In terms of anonymity, there was a stricter standard in which the participants remained as anonymous in this research study.

Results and Discussion:

This section deals with the presentation, analysis and interpretation of data gathered to carry out the objectives of this study. All these were made possible by following certain appropriate procedures so as to give the exact data and solution to each specific problem.

Table 1
Degree of Challenges Encountered by Intermediate English teachers Before the Implementation of the PHIL-IRI

Items	Mean	Interpretation
1. Delay in the approval of the budget for reproduction of materials	2.74	Moderate Degree
2. Shortage in the allocation of budget for reproduction	2.61	Moderate Degree
3. No specific plan of the school to guide conduct of the PHIL-IRI	2.18	Low Degree
4. Teachers are left to make their own plan in the conduct of PHI-IRI	2.58	Moderate Degree
5. PHIL-IRI is planned to be conducted outside regular working hours of teachers	2.68	Moderate Degree
6. Teachers are personally doing the reproduction of materials	3.61	High Degree
7. Teachers are personally spending the reproduction of materials	2.47	Low Degree
8. Teachers are personally sorting the materials	3.95	High Degree
9. The allotted time as planned is too short as this is outside regular working hours of teachers	3.55	High Degree
10. No or lack of teachers’ orientation on how to conduct PHIL-IRI	2.32	Low Degree
Sub-mean	2.87	Moderate Degree

Table 1 shows the degree of challenges encountered by Intermediate English Teachers before the implementation of the PHIL-IRI with a mean score of 2.87, interpreted as moderate degree. Item no. 8 which states that teachers are personally sorting the materials got the highest mean score of 3.95, interpreted as high degree. Meanwhile Item no. 3 states that no specific plan of the school to guide conduct of the PHIL-IRI got the lowest mean score of 2.18, interpreted as low degree. The overall mean score was 2.87, interpreted as moderate degree. According to the result, seeing the struggle of teachers in sorting the PHIL-IRI materials like spending their own resources just to caught on time, teachers use their extra miles in preparing and conducting because there is no specific scheduled and time added to the classroom program. Muhammad (2019) in his finding states the different challenges encountered by teachers in teaching the English language to learners. Some of these are disturbed environment of the class, limited teaching resources, a large number of students in the classroom, and students are bored and not interested to learn English language. He states that teaching the English language to non-English speakers is not an easy job for the teachers.

Table 2

Degree of Challenges Encountered by Intermediate English teachers During the Implementation of the PHIL-IRRI

Items	Mean	Interpretation
1. Shortage of time allotment in the conduct of PHIL-IRI	3.53	High Degree
2. Tiresome in the part of the teacher as it is conducted outside regular working hours	2.76	Moderate Degree
3. Absence of learners to come during the scheduled conduct of PHIL-IRI	2.55	Moderate Degree
4. Tardiness of learners to come during the scheduled conduct of PHIL-IRI	2.32	Low Degree
5. No supervision and monitoring conducted by school head during the administration of PHIL-IRI	2.47	Low Degree
6. No technical assistance provided during the conduct of PHIL-IRI	2.45	Low Degree
7. Unreadable printouts of the materials discovered during the conduct of PHIL-IRI	1.68	Low Degree
8. Difficulty in the part of the teachers in recording the results of PHIL-IRI	2.13	Low Degree
9. There are learners who just refuse to read	2.18	Low Degree
10. Longer days to finish the conduct of PHIL-IRI due to short span of time daily in conducting it	3.34	Moderate Degree
Sub-mean	2.49	Low Degree

Table 2 shows the degree of challenges encountered by Intermediate English Teachers before the implementation of the PHIL-IRI, with a mean score of 2.49, and interpreted as low degree. The item no. 1 which states the shortage of time allotment in the conduct of PHIL-IRI got the highest mean score of 3.53, interpreted as high degree. Meanwhile item no. 7 which states the unreadable printouts of the materials discovered during the conduct of PHIL-IRI got the lowest mean score of 1.68. The result shows that teachers need enough time in conducting the PHIL-IRI. This should be indicated in the classroom program so that teachers can effectively conduct and got the exact results.

Table 3

Degree of Challenges Encountered by Intermediate English teachers After the Implementation of the PHIL-IRI

Items	Mean	Interpretation
1. Materials are utilized to other sections after using them	2.95	Moderate Degree
2. No refund for the personal expenses in the reproduction of materials	2.13	Low Degree
3. Delayed refund for the teachers' expenses in the reproduction of materials	2.16	Low Degree
4. No analysis of results as basis for intervention	2.03	Low Degree
5. No intervention conducted after the PHIL-IRI pretest	1.87	Low Degree
6. No administrative support from the school head to address learning needs after the conduct of PHIL-IRI	2.08	Low Degree
7. No learning materials produced as intervention based on the result of PHIL-IRI pretest	2.13	Low Degree
8. Difficulty of teachers in interpreting the results of the PHIL-IRI	2.05	Low Degree
9. No budget allotted for the reproduction of intervention materials	2.24	Low Degree
10. No specific time for remediation class during regular working hours	2.37	Low Degree
Sub-mean	2.20	Low Degree

The table 3 shows the degree of challenges encountered by Intermediate English Teachers before the implementation of the PHIL-IRI, with a mean score of 2.20 interpreted as Low Degree. This implies that most of the respondents utilized the materials to other sections since most of the teachers gave interventions after the results. As indicated in table no. 5, the degree of challenges encountered by Intermediate English Teachers after the

implementation, item no. 1 states that the materials are utilized to other sections after using them got the mean score of 2.95 and interpreted as moderate degree. Item no. 5 states that no intervention conducted after the PHIL-IRI pretest got the mean score of 1.87 and interpreted as low degree.

Table 4

Degree of Challenges Encountered by Intermediate English Teachers Before the Implementation of PHIL-IRI When Grouped According to Age

Items	Younger		Older	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
1. Delay in the approval of the budget for reproduction of materials	2.90	Moderate Degree	2.56	Moderate Degree
2. Shortage in the allocation of budget for reproduction	3.00	Moderate Degree	2.17	Low Degree
3. No specific plan of the school to guide conduct of the PHIL-IRI	2.20	Low Degree	2.17	Low Degree
4. Teachers are left to make their own plan in the conduct of PHIL-IRI	2.45	Low Degree	2.72	Moderate Degree
5. PHIL-IRI is planned to be conducted outside regular working hours of teachers	2.30	Low Degree	3.11	Moderate Degree
6. Teachers are personally doing the reproduction of materials	4.05	High Degree	3.11	Moderate Degree
7. Teachers are personally spending the reproduction of materials	2.80	Moderate Degree	2.11	Low Degree
8. Teachers are personally sorting the materials	4.20	High Degree	3.67	High Degree
9. The allotted time as planned is too short as this is outside regular working hours of teachers	3.55	High Degree	3.56	High Degree
10. No or lack of teachers' orientation on how to conduct PHIL-IRI	2.50	Moderate Degree	2.11	Low Degree
Sub-means	3.00	Moderate Degree	2.73	Moderate Degree

The table 4 shows the degree of challenges encountered by the Intermediate English Teachers before the implementation of PHIL-IRI, when grouped according to age with the mean of 3.0 and 2.73 respectively, interpreted as moderate degree. It is revealed that both younger and older respondents got the high degree with a mean score of 3.55% as interpreted as high degree for the younger and 3.67% as interpreted as high degree for the older respondents in item no. 8 that teachers are personally sorting the materials. While item no. 3 which states that no specific plan of the school to guide conduct of the PHIL-IRI got the mean score of 2.20 interpreted as low degree in the younger respondents got the lowest mean score. For the older group item numbers 7 & 10 which states that teachers are personally spending the reproduction of materials and no or lack of teachers' orientation on how to conduct PHIL-IRI with the mean score of 2.11% interpreted as low degree. This implies that both younger and older respondents are personally sorting the materials. On the other hand, few of the younger respondents had no specific plan of the school to guide conduct of the PHIL-IRI. For the older respondents, some of the older respondents are personally spending the reproduction of materials and no or lack of teachers' orientation on how to conduct PHIL-IRI.

Table 5

Degree of Challenges Encountered by Intermediate English Teachers During the Implementation of the PHIL-IRI When Grouped According to Age

Items	Younger		Older	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
1. Shortage of time allotment in the conduct of PHIL-IRI	3.40	Moderate Degree	3.67	High Degree
2. Tiresome in the part of the teacher as it is conducted outside regular working hours	2.55	Moderate Degree	3.00	Moderate Degree
3. Absence of learners to come during the scheduled conduct of PHIL-IRI	2.35	Low Degree	2.78	Moderate Degree
4. Tardiness of learners to come during the scheduled conduct of PHIL-IRI	2.45	Low Degree	2.17	Low Degree
5. No supervision and monitoring conducted by school head during the administration of PHIL-IRI	2.55	Moderate Degree	2.39	Low Degree

6. No technical assistance provided during the conduct of PHIL-IRI	2.55	Moderate Degree	2.33	Low Degree
7. Unreadable printouts of the materials discovered during the conduct of PHIL-IRI	1.85	Low Degree	1.50	Low Degree
8. Difficulty in the part of the teachers in recording the results of PHIL-IRI	2.30	Low Degree	1.94	Low Degree
9. There are learners who just refuse to read	2.35	Low Degree	2.00	Low Degree
10. Longer days to finish the conduct of PHIL-IRI due to short span of time daily in conducting it	3.30	Moderate Degree	3.39	Moderate Degree
Sub-means	2.50	Moderate Degree	2.47	Low Degree

The table 5 shows the degree of challenges encountered by the Intermediate English Teachers during the implementation of PHIL-IRI when grouped according to age with the mean score of 2.50 and 2.47 respectively interpreted as Moderate Degree and Low Degree. It is revealed that shortage of time allotment in the conduct of PHIL-IRI in the young group obtained a mean score of 3.40 interpreted as moderate degree and the older group obtained a mean score of 3.67 and interpreted as high degree. Item no.7 which states that unreadable printouts of the materials discovered during the conduct of PHIL-IRI both young and old group got the lowest mean score of 1.85 for the younger group and 1.50 for the older group both interpreted as low degree. Results revealed that during the conduct of PHIL-IRI both younger and older group had a hard time in the utilization of time since regular class hour will not be used during the actual conduct of PHIL-IRI. As supported by the study of Manaog (2020) states that the news hit us hard, teachers, especially since we consciously and religiously labor six days a week in teaching our lessons to our students, teaching them with the prescribed materials and even working longer hours to comply with and submit the needed paperwork. He states that he identifies where this comes from. He attributes that the increasing number of slow readers and non-readers to a string of factors, namely: the lack of study habits among our pupils; the lack of contact hours in teaching; the effects of technology, internet and the social media; and the effects of even the Department of Education's Child Protection Policy (DepEd Order 40, series of 2012).

Table 6

Degree of Challenges Encountered by Intermediate English Teachers After the Implementation of the PHIL-IRI When Grouped According to Age

Items	Younger		Older	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
1. Materials are utilized to other sections after using them	2.85	Moderate Degree	3.06	Moderate Degree
2. No refund for the personal expenses in the reproduction of materials	2.35	Low Degree	1.89	Low Degree
3. Delayed refund for the teachers' expenses in the reproduction of materials	2.30	Low Degree	2.00	Low Degree
4. No analysis of results as basis for intervention	2.10	Low Degree	1.94	Low Degree
5. No intervention conducted after the PHIL-IRI pretest	1.80	Low Degree	1.94	Low Degree
6. No administrative support from the school head to address learning needs after the conduct of PHIL-IRI	2.20	Low Degree	1.94	Low Degree
7. No learning materials produced as intervention based on the result of PHIL-IRI pretest	2.10	Low Degree	2.17	Low Degree
8. Difficulty of teachers in interpreting the results of the PHIL-IRI	2.10	Low Degree	2.00	Low Degree
9. No budget allotted for the reproduction of intervention materials	2.30	Low Degree	2.17	Low Degree
10. No specific time for remediation class during regular working hours	2.15	Low Degree	2.61	Moderate Degree
Sub-mean	2.23	Low Degree	2.17	Low Degree

Table 6 shows the degree of challenges encountered by Intermediate English Teachers after the implementation of the PHIL-IRI according to age with the mean score of 2.23 and 2.17 respectively interpreted as low degree. Both younger and older group on item no.1 states that materials are utilized to other sections after using them with a mean score of 2.85 for younger group and 3.06 for the older group both interpreted as moderate degree. Item no. 5 states that no intervention conducted after the PHIL-IRI pretest with a mean score of 1.80 for the younger group and interpreted as low degree. For the older group, item no.2 states that no refund for the personal expenses in the reproduction of materials with a mean score of 1.89 interpreted as low degree. This means that the teachers need to secure the materials so that other sections can reuse the tool. This study showed that intervention was given to

the struggling learners and the reproduction of materials were charged by the school's Maintenance and Other Operating Expenses (MOOE).

Table 7

Degree of Challenges Encountered by Intermediate English Teachers Before the Implementation of PHIL-IRI When Grouped According to Number of Years as English Teacher

Items	Shorter		Longer	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
1. Delay in the approval of the budget for reproduction of materials	3.05	Moderate Degree	2.42	Low Degree
2. Shortage in the allocation of budget for reproduction	2.95	Moderate Degree	2.26	Low Degree
3. No specific plan of the school to guide conduct of the PHIL-IRI	2.21	Low Degree	2.16	Low Degree
4. Teachers are left to make their own plan in the conduct of PHI-IRI	2.42	Low Degree	2.74	Moderate Degree
5. PHIL-IRI is planned to be conducted outside regular working hours of teachers	2.32	Low Degree	3.05	Moderate Degree
6. Teachers are personally doing the reproduction of materials	3.89	High Degree	3.32	Moderate Degree
7. Teachers are personally spending the reproduction of materials	2.68	Moderate Degree	2.26	Low Degree
8. Teachers are personally sorting the materials	4.21	High Degree	3.68	High Degree
9. The allotted time as planned is too short as this is outside regular working hours of teachers	3.63	High Degree	3.47	Moderate Degree
10. No or lack of teachers' orientation on how to conduct PHIL-IRI	2.42	Low Degree	2.21	Low Degree
Sub-mean	2.98	Moderate Degree	2.76	Moderate Degree

Table no. 7 shows the degree of challenges encountered by Intermediate English Teachers Before the implementation of PHIL IRI according to number of years as English Teacher with the mean score of 2.98 and 2.76 respectively, interpreted as moderated degree. It is revealed that item no. 8 states that teachers are personally sorting the materials got the mean score of 4.21 for the shorter group and 3.68 for the longer group both interpreted as high degree. Item no. 3 which states that no specific plan of the school to guide conduct of the PHIL-IRI with a mean score of 2.21 for the shorter group and 2.16 for the longer group both interpreted as low degree. Study showed that both shorter and longer group were personally sorting the materials. While both longer and shorter group had an specific plan of the school to guide conduct of the PHIL-IRI.

Table 8

Degree of Challenges Encountered by Intermediate English Teachers During the Implementation of PHIL-IRI When Grouped According to Number of Years as English Teacher

Items	Shorter		Longer	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
1. Shortage of time allotment in the conduct of PHIL-IRI	3.32	Moderate Degree	3.74	High Degree
2. Tiresome in the part of the teacher as it is conducted outside regular working hours	2.26	Low Degree	3.26	Moderate Degree
3. Absence of learners to come during the scheduled conduct of PHIL-IRI	2.53	Moderate Degree	2.58	Moderate Degree
4. Tardiness of learners to come during the scheduled conduct of PHIL-IRI	2.42	Low Degree	2.21	Low Degree
5. No supervision and monitoring conducted by school head during the administration of PHIL-IRI	2.21	Low Degree	2.74	Moderate Degree
6. No technical assistance provided during the conduct of PHIL-IRI	2.47	Low Degree	2.42	Low Degree
7. Unreadable printouts of the materials discovered during the conduct of PHIL-IRI	1.95	Low Degree	1.42	Very Low Degree

8. Difficulty in the part of the teachers in recording the results of PHIL-IRI	2.11	Low Degree	2.16	Low Degree
9. There are learners who just refuse to read	2.32	Low Degree	2.05	Low Degree
10. Longer days to finish the conduct of PHIL-IRI due to short span of time daily in conducting it	3.21	Moderate Degree	3.47	Moderate Degree
Sub-mean	2.41	Low Degree	2.57	Moderate Degree

Table 8 shows the degree of challenges encountered by Intermediate English Teachers during the implementation of PHIL-IRI according to number of years with the mean of 2.41 and 2.57 interpreted as Low degree and Moderate degree respectively. In item no.1 states that the shortage of time allotment in the conduct of PHIL-IRI got the highest degree with a mean score of 3.32 for the shorter group and 3.74 for the longer group both interpreted as high degree. Item no.7 states that unreadable printouts of the materials discovered during the conduct of PHIL-IRI got the mean score of 1.95 for the shorter group interpreted as low degree and 1.42 for the longer group interpreted as very low degree. This implied that both shorter and longer group experienced shortage of time allotment during the conduct of PHIL-IRI.

Table 9

Degree of Challenges Encountered by Intermediate English Teachers After the Implementation of PHIL-IRI When Grouped According to Number of Years as English Teacher

Items	Shorter		Longer	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
1. Materials are utilized to other sections after using them	2.84	Moderate Degree	3.05	Moderate Degree
2. No refund for the personal expenses in the reproduction of materials	2.16	Low Degree	2.11	Low Degree
3. Delayed refund for the teachers' expenses in the reproduction of materials	2.21	Low Degree	2.11	Low Degree
4. No analysis of results as basis for intervention	2.05	Low Degree	2.00	Low Degree
5. No intervention conducted after the PHIL-IRI pretest	1.84	Low Degree	1.89	Low Degree
6. No administrative support from the school head to address learning needs after the conduct of PHIL-IRI	2.00	Low Degree	2.16	Low Degree
7. No learning materials produced as intervention based on the result of PHIL-IRI pretest	2.11	Low Degree	2.16	Low Degree
8. Difficulty of teachers in interpreting the results of the PHIL-IRI	1.89	Low Degree	2.21	Low Degree
9. No budget allotted for the reproduction of intervention materials	2.11	Low Degree	2.37	Low Degree
10. No specific time for remediation class during regular working hours	2.32	Low Degree	2.42	Low Degree
Sub-mean	2.15	Low Degree	2.25	Low Degree

Table no. 9 shows the degree of challenges encountered by Intermediate English Teachers after the implementation of PHIL-IRI according to number of years as English Teacher with the mean score of 2.15 and 2.25, interpreted as Low degree. The item no.1 states that materials are utilized to other sections after using them got the mean score of 2.84 for shorter group and 3.05 for longer group both interpreted as moderate degree. Item no. 5 states that no intervention conducted after the PHIL-IRI pretest with a mean score of 1.84 for the shorter group and 1.89 for the longer group both interpreted as low degree. This implied that after the implementation of PHIL-IRI the materials were utilized to other sections and interventions were also given.

Table 10

Degree of Challenges Encountered by Intermediate English Teachers Before the Implementation of PHIL-IRI When Grouped According to Highest Educational Attainment

Items	Lower		Higher	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
1. Delay in the approval of the budget for reproduction of materials	2.75	Moderate Degree	2.70	Moderate Degree
2. Shortage in the allocation of budget for reproduction	2.61	Moderate Degree	2.60	Moderate Degree

3. No specific plan of the school to guide conduct of the PHIL-IRI	2.25	Low Degree	2.00	Low Degree
4. Teachers are left to make their own plan in the conduct of PHI-IRI	2.43	Low Degree	3.00	Moderate Degree
5. PHIL-IRI is planned to be conducted outside regular working hours of teachers	2.50	Moderate Degree	3.20	Moderate Degree
6. Teachers are personally doing the reproduction of materials	3.43	Moderate Degree	4.10	High Degree
7. Teachers are personally spending the reproduction of materials	2.32	Low Degree	2.90	Moderate Degree
8. Teachers are personally sorting the materials	3.82	High Degree	4.30	High Degree
9. The allotted time as planned is too short as this is outside regular working hours of teachers	3.39	Moderate Degree	4.00	High Degree
10. No or lack of teachers' orientation on how to conduct PHIL-IRI	2.36	Low Degree	2.20	Low Degree
Sub-mean	2.79	Moderate Degree	3.10	Moderate Degree

Table 10 shows the degree of challenges encountered by Intermediate English Teachers before the implementation of PHIL-IRI according to Highest Educational Attainment, with the mean score of 2.79 and 3.10 respectively and interpreted as Moderate Degree. In item no.8 states that Teachers are personally sorting the materials with a mean score of 3.82 for the lower group interpreted as moderate degree and 4.30 for the higher group interpreted as high degree. Item no. 3 states that no specific plan of the school to guide conduct of the PHIL-IRI with a mean score of 2.25 for the lower group and 2.00 for the higher group both interpreted as low degree. This implied that before the implementation of PHIL-IRI most of the teachers were personally sorting the materials and the school had specific plan to guide conduct of the PHIL-IRI.

Table 11

Degree of Challenges Encountered by Intermediate English Teachers During the Implementation of PHIL-IRI When Grouped According to Highest Educational Attainment

Items	Lower		Higher	
	Mea n	Interpretation	n	Interpretation
1.Shortage of time allotment in the conduct of PHIL-IRI	3.50	High Degree	3.60	High Degree
2.Tiresome in the part of the teacher as it is conducted outside regular working hours	2.79	Moderate Degree	2.70	Moderate Degree
3.Absence of learners to come during the scheduled conduct of PHIL-IRI	2.68	Moderate Degree	2.20	Low Degree
4.Tardiness of learners to come during the scheduled conduct of PHIL-IRI	2.32	Low Degree	2.30	Low Degree
5.No supervision and monitoring conducted by school head during the administration of PHIL-IRI	2.43	Low Degree	2.60	Moderate Degree
6.No technical assistance provided during the conduct of PHIL-IRI	2.54	Moderate Degree	2.20	Low Degree
7.Unreadable printouts of the materials discovered during the conduct of PHIL-IRI	1.79	Low Degree	1.40	Very Low Degree
8.Difficulty in the part of the teachers in recording the results of PHIL-IRI	1.96	Low Degree	2.60	Moderate Degree
9.There are learners who just refuse to read	2.14	Low Degree	2.30	Low Degree
10.Longer days to finish the conduct of PHIL-IRI due to short span of time daily in conducting it	3.32	Moderate Degree	3.40	Moderate Degree
Sub-mean	2.50	Moderate Degree	2.45	Low Degree

Table 11 shows the degree of challenges encountered by Intermediate English Teachers during the implementation of PHIL-IRI according to Highest Educational Attainment with the mean score of 2.50 and 2.45, which interpreted as Moderate Degree and low degree respectively. Item no.1 states that shortage of time allotment in the conduct of PHIL-IRI got the mean score of 3.50 for a lower group and 3.60 for a higher group both interpreted as high degree. Item no. 7 states that unreadable printouts of the materials discovered during the conduct of PHIL-IRI with a mean score of 1.79 for the lower group interpreted as low degree and 1.40 for the higher group interpreted as very low degree. This implied that during the implementation of PHIL-IRI both lower and higher group t of the respondents

struggled the time allotted during the conduct of the PHIL-IRI and the materials were all readable and can easily be used.

Table 14

Degree of Challenges Encountered by Intermediate English Teachers After the Implementation of PHIL-IRI When Grouped According to Highest Educational Attainment

Categories	Lower Mean	Interpretation	Higher Mean	Interpretation
1. Materials are utilized to other sections after using them	3.00	Moderate Degree	2.80	Moderate Degree
2. No refund for the personal expenses in the reproduction of materials	2.11	Low Degree	2.20	Low Degree
3. Delayed refund for the teachers' expenses in the reproduction of materials	2.11	Low Degree	2.30	Low Degree
4. No analysis of results as basis for intervention	2.14	Low Degree	1.70	Low Degree
5. No intervention conducted after the PHIL-IRI pretest	2.00	Low Degree	1.50	Low Degree
6. No administrative support from the school head to address learning needs after the conduct of PHIL-IRI	1.96	Low Degree	2.40	Low Degree
7. No learning materials produced as intervention based on the result of PHIL-IRI pretest	2.18	Low Degree	2.00	Low Degree
8. Difficulty of teachers in interpreting the results of the PHIL-IRI	1.96	Low Degree	2.30	Low Degree
9. No budget allotted for the reproduction of intervention materials	2.18	Low Degree	2.40	Low Degree
10. No specific time for remediation class during regular working hours	2.46	Low Degree	2.10	Low Degree
Sub-mean	2.21	Low Degree	2.17	Low Degree

Table 14 shows the degree of challenges encountered by Intermediate English Teachers after the implementation of PHIL-IRI according to Highest Educational Attainment with the mean score of 2.21 and 2.17 interpreted as low degree respectively. Items no.1 states that materials are utilized to other sections after using them with a mean score of 3.00 for the lower group and 2.80 for the higher group interpreted as moderate degree. Items no. 6 states that no administrative support from the school head to address learning needs after the conduct of PHIL-IRI and item no.8 which states the difficulty of teachers in interpreting the results of the PHIL-IRI both with a mean score of 1.96 for the lower group and both interpreted as low degree and item no. 5 states that no intervention conducted after the PHIL-IRI pretest with a mean score of 1.50 for the higher group and interpreted as low degree. This implied that after the implementation of PHIL-IRI materials were utilized by other sections and there were support from the administrative staff in addressing the learning needs and results were easily interpreted by the teachers.

Table 15

Level of Learners' Reading Performance Based on Grade Levels

Grade Level	Mean	Interpretation
4	66.49	Instructional
5	66.65	Instructional
6	68.92	Instructional
Total	67.31	Instructional

Table 15 shows the level of learner's reading performance when grouped according to grade level with a total of 67.31 with the same interpretation as instructional level. The grade 6 group with a mean score of 68.92 while grade 5 got a mean score of 66.65 and grade 4 got a mean score of 66.49. This means that the learners reading performance in the intermediate level belongs to the instructional level, and this conclude that these learners need more reading intervention in order to reach the independent level.

Table 16

Difference in the Degree of Challenges Encountered by Intermediate English Teachers Before the Implementation of The PHIL-IRI When Grouped and Compared According to the Aforementioned Variable

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	20	20.88	152.50	0.426		Not Significant
	Older	18	17.97				
No. of Years as English Teacher	Shorter	19	20.95	153.00	0.435	0.05	Not Significant
	Longer	28	18.55				
Highest Educational Attainment	Lower	10	22.15	113.50	0.386		Not Significant
	Higher	8	4.29				
	Longer	9	4.32				

Table 16 shows the data on significant difference in the degree of challenges encountered by Intermediate English Teachers before the implementation of the PHIL-IRI when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables. As can be gleaned on the table 16 in determining the significant difference in the degree of challenges encountered by Intermediate English Teachers before the implementation of the PHIL-IRI, results showed the computed H test which is 152.50 (age), 153.00 (no. of years as English Teacher), and 113.50 (Highest Educational Attainment) with a computed p value of 0.05 interpreted as “not significant”. Therefore, the hypothesis of the study was rejected. It is therefore interpreted that all respondents regardless to age, number of years as English Teacher and Highest Educational Attainment does not significantly differed when group accordingly before the implementation of PHIL-IRI.

Table 17

Comparative Analysis in the Degree of Challenges Encountered by Intermediate English Teachers During the Implementation of The PHIL-IRI When Grouped and Compared According to the Aforementioned Variable

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	20	19.28	175.50	0.897		Significant
	Older	18	19.75				
No. of Years as English Teacher	Shorter	19	17.95	151.00	0.402	0.05	Not Significant
	Longer	19	21.05				
Highest Educational Attainment	Lower	28	19.84	130.50	0.757		Not Significant
	Higher	10	18.55				

Table 17 shows the comparative analysis on the degree of challenges encountered by Intermediate English Teachers during the implementation of the PHIL-IRI when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables. When grouped according to age the younger obtained a mean score of 19.28 and the older group obtained a mean score of 19.75, the computed p value was 0.897 interpreted as “significant level” which signifies that there is a significant difference. Therefore, the hypothesis of the study was accepted. When grouped according to no. of years as English Teacher the shorter group obtained a mean score of 17.95 and the longer group obtained a mean score of 21.05, the computed p value of 0.402 interpreted as not significant. When grouped according to highest educational attainment, lower group obtained a mean score of 19.84 and the higher group obtained a mean score of 18.55, with the p value of 0.757 interpreted as “not significant”. Therefore, the hypothesis of the study is rejected. The above signified that the no. of years as English Teacher and the highest educational attainment

Table 18

Comparative Analysis in the Degree of Challenges Encountered by Intermediate English Teachers After the Implementation of The PHIL-IRI When Grouped and Compared According to the Aforementioned Variable

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	20	19.43	178.50	0.965		Not Significant
	Older	18	19.58				
No. of Years as English Teacher	Shorter	19	18.74	166.00	0.686	0.05	Not Significant
	Longer	19	20.26				
Highest Educational Attainment	Lower	28	19.70	134.50	0.858		Not Significant
	Higher	10	18.95				

Table 18 shows the comparative analysis on the degree of challenges encountered by Intermediate English Teachers after the implementation of the PHIL-IRI when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables. When grouped according to age the younger obtained a mean score of 19.43 and the older group obtained a mean score of 19.58, the computed p value was 0.965 interpreted as “not significant level” which signifies that there is no significant difference. Therefore, the hypothesis of the study was rejected. When grouped according to no. of years as English Teacher the shorter group obtained a mean score of 18.74 and the longer group obtained a mean score of 20.26, the computed p value of 0.686 interpreted as not significant. When grouped according to highest educational attainment, lower group obtained a mean score of 19.70 and the higher group obtained a mean score of 18.95, with the p value of 0.858 interpreted as “not significant”. Therefore, the hypothesis of the study is rejected.

Table 19

Relationship Between the Degree of Challenges Encountered by Intermediate English Teachers and the Level of Learners’ Reading Performance

Correlates	N	rho	Level of Sig	p-value	Interpretation
Degree of Challenges	38	-0.115	0.05	0.505	Not significant
Level of Reading Performance	38				

Table 19 shows the relationship between the degree of challenges encountered by Intermediate English Teachers and the level of learner’s reading performance. As can be gleaned on the table 18 in determining the relationship between the degree of challenges and the level of reading performance, results showed that computed test is not significant.

Conclusions:

In conclusions, the degree of challenges encountered by Intermediate English Teacher in the Implementation of PHIL-IRI in relation to learner’s reading performance in the phases of before implementation, during implementation and after implementation. During implementation the degree of challenges are in moderate. While during and after implementation the respondents are in low degree. This meant that the challenges that they encountered before the implementation is in moderate degree and can be tolerated.

The degree of challenges encountered by Intermediate English Teacher in the implementation of PHIL-IRI in relation to learners reading performance when grouped according to the aforementioned variables. In age variable before implementation is in moderate degree, during implementation the younger is in moderate degree and the older in low degree. After implementation is also in low degree. It entailed that most of the younger respondents had experience moderate challenges before, during and after implementation.

In the level of learners reading performance based on grade levels it is evident that most of the learners are on instructional level.

In the degree of challenges encountered by Intermediate English Teachers when they are grouped and compared based to the aforementioned variables: before and after implementation age, number of years as English Teacher and highest educational attainment was not significantly related. It was in the during implementation that age is significantly related.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions of the study regarding the significant relationship between the challenges encountered by Intermediate English Teachers during the implementation of PHIL-IRI and the variable of age, the following recommendations are proposed:

1. **Targeted Professional Development:** Develop specific training programs for younger teachers to enhance their instructional and classroom management skills related to PHIL-IRI.
2. **Mentorship Programs:** Pair younger teachers with experienced mentors to provide guidance and support throughout the implementation process.
3. **Regular Feedback Mechanisms:** Establish channels for ongoing teacher feedback to identify and address challenges promptly.
4. **Resource Allocation:** Ensure equal access to instructional materials and resources for all teachers, regardless of age.
5. **Flexible Training Approaches:** Offer varied training formats to accommodate different learning styles and schedules.
6. **Focus on Collaborative Learning:** Promote collaborative methods such as team teaching and co-planning to tackle challenges collectively.
7. **Incorporate Teacher Feedback in Policy Making:** Involve teachers in shaping policies based on their experiences and needs.
8. **Further Research on Demographic Variables:** Investigate other factors like geographic location and socio-economic status to gain a deeper understanding of challenges faced by teachers.

Acknowledgment

The researcher is really grateful because she managed to finish her research within the given time frame with the help and guidance of her adviser Dr. Lisa C. Cañedo. To all people who extended their help in any way, thank you.

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